

Buddhist discourse in the Great Tang Records of the Western Regions by Xuanzang

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Abstract

This article aims to develop theoretical issues in travel writing based on a literary approach to the topic of travel writing about journeys made by monks. Buddhist discourse is the cognitive basis for accessing the scholarly value of travel writing. The Buddhist discourse in the travel writings of monks whose journey as a religious ethical practice is grounded in Buddhist discourse theory and doctrine. We do a method of document review and comprehensive analysis to identify Buddhist discourse in the narrative of the journey... Case studies were on the works *Great Tang Records of the Western Regions* by Duong Huyen Trang. This research focuses on the diversity and unity of Buddhist discourse through the selection of forms of expression in travel writing, thereby creating the distinctive features of travel writing authored by monks. The issues explored in this article will offer a fresh perspective on Buddhist travelogues, a significant literary component in the realm of human literature.

Keywords: Buddhist discourse, Buddhist pilgrimage, travel writing, monks, discourse analysis.

1. Introduction

Buddhist travel writing is a part of travel writing, representing Eastern travel writing, born in the medieval literature period with the characteristics of indistinguishable literature - history - philosophy. Travel writing is a journey expressed in text, where language and its use are a means of recreating the journey according to the subject's perception of the world. To consider travel writing as discourse is to view the text as mediating relationships between language users: not only relationships of speech but also of consciousness, ideology, roles, and class. Travel writing is no longer an object but it becomes an action or a process. This is also the issue of approaching Buddhist pilgrimage travel writing in terms of literature, the cognitive basis for analyzing the discourse of travel writing works. To consolidate and practice the theory of Buddhist travel writing, we analyze discourse with the *Great Tang Records of the Western Regions* by monk Xuanzang.

2. Literature review

Human history has witnessed great human journeys and along with it comes a genre of literature about journeys called travel writing. After a long time, from its inception until the late 20th century, travel writing was not recognized by literature as a genre but only as a subgenre that existed in the form of documents, and paraliterary. Contemporary travel writing research has paid attention to the issue of the genre of travel writing and has established travel writing as a genre in its own right. Thanks to the birth and companionship of different journeys, it seems the existence of travel writing has made the world larger and larger. In general, from the initial

awareness of travel writing as a subgenre of literature, now travel writing has been recognized by many people as a “genre of genres” (Rubies and Bacon, 2000:6) and as “a common home” (Thompson, 2011), travel writing contains many different literary genres. Due to its mystery, diversity, and richness, travel writing is approached by many different cultural and literary theories. This has made travel writing exist in a potential form like other literary genres.

Recent research on travel writing shows that travel writing is located between the boundaries of literature and culture. However, there is an obvious fact that the need to explore the world and discover ourselves is equivalent; people use the journey to perceive the world including themselves; and use language to recreate it as a dialogue about experience to satisfy this need. This means the need to travel and reflect on that travel in linguistic forms are literary method of exploring the world.

From a cultural perspective, religious journeys have formed a part of pilgrimage literature, of which travel writing is a typical representative. Basumatary (2018) said “Religion and travel stories are always linked together because that is where travel began to attract religious pilgrimages”. Historical pilgrimages have left behind many travel writing works whose content forms the theme of religious pilgrimage travel. Pilgrimage has become a tradition of major religions in the world. Religions that have holy places and legends about the origins of their supreme beings promote regular pilgrimages. Pilgrimage becomes the subject of various cultural discourses, of which travel writing is a form of religious discourse.

In recent times, pilgrimage travel writing has become an object of research that has attracted the attention of many scientists. Research on travel writing about journeys has been approached in many fields. A cross-cultural approach to explore the motivational elements of journeys to religious sites or events, examining religious, cultural, traditional, spiritual, and landscape patterns, often interacting together in the intention and decision to start the trip with studies such as Kaewumpai 2018; Kim et al. 2018; Olsen 2013; Terzidou et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2016; Abbate and Nuovo 2013; Amaro et al. 2018; Drule et al. 2015; Hughes et al 2013,... Approaching religion to study the motivations, concerns, and spiritual or cultural needs that religious centres arouse for pilgrimages, there are studies such as Abbate and Nuovo 2013; Amaro et al. 2018; Raj 2012,... Historical approaches to travel writing works whose content reflects the cultural heritage, architectural, cultural, or artistic values include studies such as Fernandes et al. 2012; Geary 2018; Musa et al. 2017; Hughes et al 2013; Hyde and Harman 2011; Ramírez and Fernández 2018; Shinde 2007... Approaching the geographical aspect of discovering places and relics on the journey, there are studies such as Markus 1994; Sotinel 2005; Digance 2003; Drijvers 2018,... Approaching the purpose and economic motives of pilgrimage travel writing works include studies such as Simone-Charteris and Boyd 2010; Tobon et al. 2013; Vukonic 2002; Egresi et al. 2014; Olsen 2012; Raj and Griffin 2015; Shackley 2001... In general, research on pilgrimage travel writing tends to focus on documentary research rather than approaching travel writing from a literary perspective. Travel writing about pilgrimage often explores religious dialogue with the world of the pilgrimage subject through various discourses.

3. Discourse and travel writing

Discourse is a way of looking at language as an action structure instead of a formal structure. Therefore, discourse is a unit of speech when placing text in the context of speaking and communication. While in the case of verbal communication the roles of both change, each

person becoming speaker and receiver respectively, in written discourse this does not happen. Written discourse involves the absence of the reader at the time of communication. This will lead to a gap in the timing of giving and receiving information between communicating characters. Discourse follows the organizational rules that exist in a given social group, related to the composition of the text, the length of the utterance, etc. (Dumitrascu, 2021). The purpose of discourse is to demonstrate linguistic behaviour that creates a difference, or a transformation, about the listener.

Discourse is an active form of language, representing the practice of the communication function of language. Every utterance is a linguistic action that takes place in a certain context to change a certain situation. Linguistic acts are part of a certain type of discourse and aim to create a transformation involving the listener. Discourse is interactive, not only promoting interaction but containing interaction; because in a discourse there are both speakers and listeners, writers and readers. Discourse depends on context because context ensures discourse exists in both content and form. The biggest context is the social context, which sets the discourse within standards to match the social norms that the discourse must comply with.

In sociology, discourse is defined as “any practice (found in various forms) through which individuals imbue meaning into reality” (Ruiz, 2009). From the perspective of ethical discourse, Habermas (1992) argues that, when we perform a speech act, we simultaneously make three valid assertions: an assertion about the truth of propositions, an assertion about normative correctness, and an assertion of truthfulness.

Discourse in travel writing is mainly narrative discourse. Narrative discourse is a discourse that recounts events, usually in the past, using speech, movement, and action verbs to describe a series of events that happen together and are often concentrated on one or more actors through linguistic acts (Longacre, 1990). Through the discourse of a journey, the author has influenced the reader of travel writing to become an observer, following the author's journey to see the strange things that make him interested heart.

Approaching discourse analysis with travel writing to see the entire story of the journey told in writing as a form of dialogue between the subject of the journey and the reader. In other words, travel writing is the author's words to someone who is following his or her journey. The diversity of readers forces the author to choose different forms of expression. This makes travel writing capable of using many forms of language to express the journey story in different ways. The context of the words about the journey is the realization of the social context at the time the author wrote about his journey. The time and space of the statement present in the work of travel writing is the entire social context. Therefore, the images depicted in travel writing are realistic, recreated images of memories.

Travel writing connects two inseparable elements: the journey and the discourse of travel. The uniqueness of each travel writing work is created by these two factors. The language expressing the journey is more personal than an objective narrative, so travel discourse is a way to reflect the world of travel writing. It is a wonderful combination between the objectivity of the journey and the subjectivity of the forms of travel discourse. Because the world of travel writing is both a world of extroversion and a world of introversion, travel writing discourse also has two types: extroverted discourse and introverted discourse. Thus, the world reflected in travel writing is the objective reality of the subjective world. Travel writing helps people realize that two worlds coexist within one person: the physical world and the spiritual world. These

two worlds must both obey objective laws and subjective laws and aesthetic norms. Up to now, researchers have paid more attention to the reality described in travel writing instead of focusing on the reality reflected. This is the trend of receiving travel writing in the form of mapping the journey. On the other hand, when faced with a large and complex world, human eyes can cover many things, while travel discourse does not allow and is not capable of expressing everything people see. This shows that travel writing is a way for people to dialogue with the world to dialogue with themselves through the journey character who is also the subject of the journey.

4. Buddhist discourse

The word Buddha means Awakened One, comes from the Sanskrit root “budh” which means 'awakened', i.e. enlightenment. The Buddha was a person who was completely “enlightened,” as if having just passed through a deep sleep, to discover that suffering, like a dream, had ended. The historical Buddha was not a god, a prophet, or any kind of supernatural being, he was a human being like everyone else. But he was an exception because he discovered a path that anyone could follow, provided they were so inclined. That is the path to achieving true wisdom, compassion, and liberation from suffering. Through his efforts, Buddha found the cause of all suffering and the path to its liberation. His followers kept that path open. The Buddha spent most of his life preaching the Dharma. He did not need to write Sutras or compile books, he only needed to speak them out to enlighten sentient beings and Buddhists. The entire philosophy of Buddhism about humans is to view human life as a path that everyone must walk, go through all suffering, and overcome to reach enlightenment. At the heart of Buddhist teachings is the theory of the “Middle Way” between sensual indulgence and harsh asceticism, leading to Nirvana, which is the path of practice to escape ignorance, craving, and rebirth. birth and suffering (Laumakis, 2008).

In Buddhist thought, the word "path" has many meanings depending on each specific case. The philosophical tradition of Abhidhamma refers to achieving the stages on the path to enlightenment especially the moment of enlightenment. Following this path is to find the means of liberation and escape from wandering. It also refers to the attainment of four hierarchical spiritual states, the final state of which is full enlightenment: stream-entry, the moment when one first realizes the path, once-returner, non-returner, and sainthood Arhat. (Shaw, 2015)

The road is symbolized by space. The larger the space and the longer the path, the more likely it is to cause suffering. Passing through space easily is the result of a process of training, cultivating, and practising the Dharma. Space is represented through mountains, rivers, and rugged terrain. Buddhist discourse in travel writing conventionally "transcends space" not to overcome the length of the road but the estimate distance: how many miles away, how many miles away. The convention of this type of space shows that the path that the monk has traversed in the hardships of pilgrimage is not a process but a result.

So “the path” applies to the daily life practice of a Buddhist, the path leading to the cessation of suffering and the ultimate result of all the elements of the path in the enlightened mind: only enlightenment reveals it fully. Travelling and moving from place to place are certainly not the only analogies used by the Buddha to describe his teachings. Metaphors and similes in Buddhism tend to be used in a variety of ways, including narrative, description, and myth. But the idea that the way we behave, speak, think, and treat others sets us on a certain path and gives us the means to travel and that this path will eventually lead to the cessation of

suffering, indicates the deep level of connection of movement in a certain direction with the means and ends of spiritual development (Shaw, 2015).

In Buddhist discourse, words related to the more directional form of travel are also used to describe how we can free ourselves from that samsara. The Buddha's teachings are likened to a path that Buddha found just as a man can cross an overgrown path in the forest, leading to a beautiful forgotten city. (Gethin, 1992)

His teachings are summarized in the Noble Eightfold Path, a method of training the mind that includes moral training and kindness towards others, as well as meditative practices such as sensory restraint, and mindfulness. The Buddha's preaching was associated with recruiting disciples and establishing a sangha. During the last 40 years or so of his life, Buddha is said to have travelled in the Ganges Delta in what is now Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and southern Nepal, teaching a wide range of people: from nobles to servants, ascetics, virtuous and family heads, murderers like Angulimala, and cannibals like Alavaka (Gethin, 1998; Strong, 2001). Dharma preaching or Dharma preaching is characteristic of Buddhist discourse. Through sermons, Buddhist stories and legends are told to educate and enlighten sentient beings. However, preaching the Dharma must be authenticated, so the Buddha's travels were not just to preach the Dharma but to practice the Dharma. Thus, preaching and travelling are the foundation of Buddhist discourse in travel writing.

Buddhist discourse has both the characteristics of travel discourse and unique features with religious elements. Regarding travel discourse, the character of the journey is often present in the story or the first-person account of the journey. Where and how the person makes the journey, overcoming many high mountains and abysses is recounted as an explicit method of Buddhist discourse. By stringing together the locations and spaces of the journey, one can sketch the route the monk went through from the time he started until he returned to his old place. Different from normal travel discourse, Buddhist discourse in travel writing often bears the mark of Buddhism in general and Buddha in particular. This mark appears through symbolic images (pagodas, stupas, Buddha statues, Buddha relics,...) or philosophical stories heard on the road about the law of cause and effect life, and reincarnation.

Buddhist discourse in travel writing is related to Buddhist teachings. The stories and descriptions of people, landscapes, customs, habits, and personality traits of strange and mysterious people are a reflection of the outside world, "other than us" and do not interfere. by thought, without praise or criticism, with disdain. In the process of enlightenment, practitioners must go through three stages: the first stage is awareness, which means knowing the rules to act correctly and orienting the goal of action; The second stage is "overcoming oneself"; The third stage is complete enlightenment, that is, reaching the realm, that is, transcendence. Travel is both a symbol of carrying out the practice path and a method of practice with the idea of reaching the realm. Therefore, Buddhist travel crosses cultural and other borders to reach the destination of the journey as an act of practice (Deeg, 2023). The practitioner's overcoming of vast space and time, full of hardships and challenges, is considered "overcoming oneself" to become transcendent. Although these concepts are valid and would work in many Buddhist contexts, the discursive use of the term is limited to philosophical-doctrinal texts and exegetical literature (Deeg, 2023). Concretizing the Buddhist metaphor of 'overcoming', this often refers to very specific natural or semi-natural barriers such as rivers, oceans, mountains/ridges, or forests (jungles) that people arrive or enter – in some cases also leave – a place or area of higher

(transcendent) religious significance. The Buddhist journey is a journey beyond borders. In addition to natural borders, and cultural borders, there is also "our border". These external and internal boundaries of Buddhist discourse are expressed through descriptions of space, places, stories, events, and other lyrical elements. The dialogue between the monks is not only with the potential tourists but also with culture and spirituality to create a form of Buddhist discourse in travel writing. Buddhist discourse exists in Buddhist literature, of which Buddhist travel writing is only a representative case. Kurniawati and Atikurrahman (2021) argue that the process of creating literary works cannot be separated from human life experiences. That is because subjectivity has deeper intimacy and relevance that can provide insights not found in objective observations (Dwijayanti & Putra, 2020).

In travel writing, although not always, it is often fully linked to some specific space, place, or place of religious importance or significance that can be understood as referring to the transcendent. This raises questions about the role and function of built space in Buddhist travel writing in general and more specifically about "transcendence - impermanence - difference" (Dennerlein, 2009).

According to Bodhi (1989), elsewhere in the Pāli canon, the idea of a wilderness is used to describe a state of doubt and the kind of doubt that undermines authentic search and investigation: in the Sāmaññaphala, the same word, *kantāra*, is used in an example describing overcoming five difficult conditions. Obstacles to the practice of meditation and a healthy and skilful mind (*kusalacitta*). Placing it as the fifth relevant example shows, as the comments have pointed out, a connection with doubt, the fifth obstacle. (p,145)

In Buddhist travel writing discourse, Buddhist terms are widely used. Repetition in narration that reflects space and route is often conventional, such as the sentence "from ... to ... about ... miles is (place, monument, mountain), rivers, lakes,...)". This type of sentence not only measures the length and magnitude of space, it shows the continuity and continuity of life that no practitioner dares to ignore. Repetition in the narrative structure of the journey means that the places that have been visited are no longer strange or new to the journeying character; It also means that the miserable or happy scenes of life in the world are never strange to those who practice the Dharma.

5. Buddhist Discourse in the Great Tang Records on the Western Regions

The Great Tang Records on the Western Regions is a travel text written by Xuanzang (602 – 664) during the Tang Dynasty in the seventh century after he returned from a journey from Chang'an to India to find Buddhist scriptures in 19 years. This work of travel writing is a report written by order of Emperor Tai Zong. The travel report describes the Buddhism, history, geography, culture, society, and customs of the countries of Central Asia and India in the medieval period. A few centuries earlier, Faxian (337 - 422) also made a pilgrimage to India and Southeast Asian countries to find Buddhist scriptures. Faxian's memoirs of this journey in *A Record of Buddhist Kingdoms* are considered a remarkable independent account of early Buddhism in India. However, it has not left an impression on generations of readers about the journey to Buddha's homeland like Xuanzang's *The Great Tang Records on the Western Regions*. Therefore, when reading Xuanzang's work in comparison with Faxian's records, Sykes (1841) exclaimed:

His [Xuanzang's] narrative has the drawback of being inflated and prolix. He is puerilely superstitious and teems with absurd legends, and is altogether destitute of that simplicity and good faith which characterize Fa hian (P.322).

Although it has been criticized in the past, The Great Tang Records on the Western Regions is a famous Buddhist travel writing of all time. The pilgrimage story of monk Huyen Trang from the perspective of discourse analysis is a reflection of culture through Buddhist discourse.

From a discursive perspective, The Great Tang Records on the Western Regions is both a report on Xuanzang's search for Buddhist scriptures with the Royal title Tai Zong, and a sermon about the land of Buddhism. Huyen Trang's travel report is both a report and a work of cultural and geographical research. The discourse of researching the culture and geography of the countries and territories of the Western Regions, outside the Dai Tang national border, created a large space containing the path that Xuanzang crossed. The author recounts a pilgrimage through 110 kingdoms from Xinjiang to Persia, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka. Reporting to the king the places visited, seen, heard, and experienced is a linguistic action in this work of travel writing. Accordingly, the report is presented in a way that presents countries as tourist-guiding discourses. Each country and territory that the author visits is identified, the size of the kingdom and capital, climatic and topographical characteristics, livestock and crop specialities, people and personalities, and language. language and customs. Territories are connected by the distance of the journey. Therefore, from one kingdom to another are strung together and interspersed with descriptions of landscapes, human stories, and Buddhist legends.

In her account of what she saw and heard in a strange land, Huyen Trang paid attention to describing people in terms of appearance, traditional costumes, and personalities in all different social classes. The author can draw boundaries for social classes through descriptions of clothing and external characteristics:

People of the kṣatriya (military and ruling class) and the brahman (priestly class) castes are pure and simple in lodging and clean and frugal. The dress and ornaments of the kings and ministers are very ostentatious. Garlands and coronets studded with gems are their headdresses, and rings, bracelets, and necklaces are their bodily ornaments. The wealthy merchants use only bracelets. Most people go barefoot; few wear shoes. They stain their teeth red or black, have closely cropped hair, pierce their earlobes, and have long noses and large eyes.

In describing human characters, the author always shows compassion. From the perspective of a monk, Huyen Trang realized that the character of a community in the Buddha's land was the inner good nature of people who looked rude and violent on the outside:

Although the people are violent and impetuous by temperament they are plain and honest. They never accept any wealth without considering the propriety of the action but give others more than what is required by righteousness. They fear retribution for sins in future lives and make light of the benefits they enjoy in the present. They do not engage in treachery and are creditable in keeping their promises.

When visiting pagodas and stupas, Huyen Trang always learns about traces or stories about the Buddha.

Two li to the east of the capital city there is a stupa built by King Aśoka that is over three hundred feet high with piled-up stones, on which there are marvellous sculptures. This was the place where [in a former life] Śākya Bodhisattva once met Dīpaṃkara Buddha and spread a piece of deerskin and his hair to cover the muddy ground [for Dīpaṃkara to tread on], and received a prediction of Buddhahood from him. Although it has passed through a kalpa of destruction the ancient trace remains intact. On fast days various kinds of flowers descend on the spot and multitudes of the common people vie with one another in making offerings [to the stupa].

Whether the stupa was built by the king or by disciples, every stupa is associated with the story of Buddha. Through this narrative, Xuanzang realized the life of Buddha in Buddhist relics and expressed his own experience when making a pilgrimage to the Buddha's land. Many stories heard or witnessed by the author are narrated in a Dharma teaching style to educate and save Buddhist sentient beings in wisdom and compassion. Buddhist narratives interpreted sermons have turned the journey story into a teaching sutra. There are also many cases where Buddhist stories are told as fairy tales, and at the same time recreated in the form of dialogue.

About ten li to the south of the royal city is a great monastery built by a previous king of this country for the arhat Vairocana (“Universal Shining” in Chinese). Formerly, when the Buddha-dharma had not yet spread to this country, the arhat came here and stayed in the wood, sitting in meditation. Someone saw him and was amazed by his appearance and garments. He reported the matter to the king, who came in person to see the arhat and said, “Who are you, staying alone in the solitary wood?” The arhat said, “I am a disciple of the Tathāgata and I live alone, practising meditation. O King, you should perform meritorious deeds to propagate the Buddha’s teachings and build a monastery for the assembly of monks.” The king said, “What are the virtues of the Tathāgata and what divine powers does he possess that made you dwell like a bird in the wood and practice his teachings so assiduously?” The arhat said in reply, “The Tathāgata has compassion for all creatures of the four kinds of birth and guides all living beings of the three realms, either overtly or covertly, in the states of existence or extinction. Those who follow his Dharma will become free of birth and death, while those who do not believe in it will be entangled in the net of passion.” The king said, “Truly, as you have said, this matter is beyond verbal discussion. Since he is a great saint he may as well appear in physical form so that I might see him. Once I have seen him I will build a monastery, believe in him as my refuge, and propagate his teachings.” The arhat said, “After you have completed the construction of a monastery you will receive his spiritual response.” Hopeful, the king agreed to build the monastery. When the construction was completed people from far and near assembled to celebrate the occasion as a religious function, but they lacked the instrument to be sounded for summoning the monks. The king said to the arhat, “Now the monastery is completed but where is the Buddha?” The arhat said, “Work with utmost sincerity; the holy evidence is not far off.” The king then prayed and worshipped and suddenly an image of the Buddha descended from the air and handed an instrument to him. Thereafter the king piously believed in the Buddha and propagated his teachings.

Based on discourse analysis, Huyen Trang's travel story refers to two issues: the birth of the monastery and the king's enlightenment. These two issues have a cause-and-effect relationship. The king met the Arhat, who practised for enlightenment, and who was the

embodiment of Buddha's karma. The king's construction of a monastery was a way to create karma based on his faith in Buddhism. The stupa was built but required the king's devotion to Buddhism. The Buddha's epiphany was the result of the king's faith and orientation to Buddha. Thus, the king sowed good causes and received beautiful results. Thus, the author does not describe how big, beautiful, and solemn the monastery is, but through this Dharma preaching story, readers can imagine a majestic and solemn monastery. But it was an empty monastery, without Buddha, and not a place of worship. No Buddha from outside flew into the temple or sat there to receive offerings from sentient beings. Buddha's epiphany is the result of a process of enlightenment of monks and sentient beings. A large temple may not have a Buddha, but a sincere heart and enlightenment will give birth to a Buddha. Buddha is enlightenment and only enlightenment can realize that Buddha is coming to us.

6. Conclusions

Buddhist discourse runs throughout the entire work *The Great Tang Records on the Western Regions* through the speech of the journeyman character Xuanzang. Thanks to that, the narrator's position is clearly expressed in the work through two forms of discourse: cultural geographical research and Buddhist sermons. This proves that Buddhist travel writing is formed by two types of discourse: cultural discourse and Buddhist discourse. Thus, *The Great Tang Records on the Western Regions* by Huyen Trang is not a simple travel story but an integration of two stories: worldly and religious. Corresponding to these two stories are two ways of expressing discourse: cultural discourse and Buddhist discourse. The narration addresses two audiences: the king (Tai Zong) and Buddhist disciples. This wonderful integration makes the work no longer an ordinary pilgrimage story but a form of Buddhist discourse that mythologizes the Buddhist pilgrimage story, making it sparkling and magical, half false and half real.

References

- Abbate, Costanza, and Santo Nuovo (2013). Motivation and Personality Traits for Choosing Religious Tourism. A Research on the Case of Medjugorje. *Current Issues in Tourism* 16: 501–6.
- Abbate, Costanza, and Santo Nuovo (2013). Motivation and Personality Traits for Choosing Religious Tourism. A Research on the Case of Medjugorje. *Current Issues in Tourism* 16: 501–6.
- Amaro, Suzanne, Angela Antunes, and Carla Henriques (2018). A Closer Look at Santiago de Compostela's Pilgrims through the Lens of Motivations. *Tourism Management* 64: 271–80.
- Amaro, Suzanne, Angela Antunes, and Carla Henriques (2018). A Closer Look at Santiago de Compostela's Pilgrims through the Lens of Motivations. *Tourism Management* 64: 271–80.
- Basumatary, B.B. (2018). Importance of travel writing in literature. *International Journal of Advance Research, Ideas and Innovations in Technology*, 4, 760-3.
- Bodhi, Bhikkhu (1989). *The Sāmaññaphala sutta and its commentaries*, Kandy..
- Deeg, M. (2023). "Chapter 2 Transcending Space: Buddhist Travelogues across Cultural and Other Borders". In *Stepping Back and Looking Ahead: Twelve Years of Studying Religious Contact at the Käte Hamburger Kolleg Bochum*. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004549319_004
- Dennerlein, Katrin (2009). *Narratologie des Raumes* (Berlin, New York: De Gruyter.
- Digance, Justine (2003). Pilgrimage at Contested Sites. *Annals of Tourism Research* 30: 143–59.

- Drijvers, J. W. (2018). Travel and Pilgrimage Literature. In S. McGill, & E. J. Watts (Eds.), *A Companion to Late Antique Literature* (pp. 359-372). (Blackwell Companions to the Ancient World). Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118830390.ch22>
- Drule, Alexandra, Mihai Băcilă, Raluca Ciornea, and Alexandru Chiș (2015). Segmenting Visitors Encountered at Sacred Sites Based on Travelling Motivations and Constraints. *Current Science* 109: 256–70.
- Dumitrascu E. (2021). The Discursive Features of the Written Tourism Discourse Specific to the Travel Guide. *“Ovidius” University Annals, Economic Sciences Series*, Volume XXI, Issue 2 /2021,273-7.
- Dwijayanti, T. A., & Putra, C. R. W. (2020). Dunia Eropa dalam Novel I Am Sarahza Karya HanumSalsabiela Rais dan Rangga Almahendra. *Metasastra*, 12(2), 151–62.
- Egresi, Istvan, Fatih Kara, and Büsa Bayram (2014). Economic Impact of Religious Tourism in Mardin, Turkey. *Journal of Economics and Business Research* 18: 7–22.
- Fernandes, Carlos, Elsa Pimenta, Francisco Gonçalves, and Susana Rachão (2012). A New Research Approach for Religious Tourism: The Case Study of The Portuguese Route to Santiago. *International Journal of Tourism Policy* 4: 83–94.
- Geary, David (2018). India’s Buddhist Circuit (s): A Growing Investment Market for a “Rising” Asia. *International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage* 6: 6.
- Gethin R. M.L (1992)., *The Buddhist Path to Awakening, A Study of the Bodhi-Pakkhiyā Dhammā* (London, New York and Cologne), 223-6.
- Gethin, Rupert, M.L. (1998), *Foundations of Buddhism*, Oxford University Press
- Habermas J. (1992), *Between Facts and Norms*. The MIT Press.
- Hughes, Karen, Nigel Bond, and Roy Ballantyne (2013). Designing and Managing Interpretive Experiences at Religious Sites: Visitors’ Perceptions of Canterbury Cathedral. *Tourism Management* 36: 210–20.
- Hyde, Kenneth F., and Serhat Harman (2011). Motives for a Secular Pilgrimage to the Gallipoli Battlefields. *Tourism Management* 32: 1343–51.
- Kaewumpai, Issara. 2018. The Influence of Personality on Tourist Behaviors: The Study of Motivations, Satisfaction, and Loyalty. *AU-GSB e-JOURNAL* 10: 54.
- Kim, Bona, and Aeongseop Kim (2018). Hierarchical Value Map of Religious Tourists Visiting the Vatican City/Rome. *Tourism Geographies*, 1–22.
- Kurniawati, N., & Atikurrahman, M. (2021). Le Flâneur du tiers monde: diri, liyan, dan kisah perjalanan dalam Bon Voyage Monsieur Le Président! *SULUK: Jurnal Bahasa, Sastra, Dan Budaya*, 3(1), 72–84.
- Laumakis, Stephen (2008), *An Introduction to Buddhist philosophy*, Cambridge; New York: Cambridge University Press, ISBN 978-0-521-85413-9
- Longacre, Robert E. 1990. *Storyline concerns and word order typology in East and West Africa*. Los Angeles: University of California at Los Angeles.
- Markus, Robert A. (1994). How on earth could places become holy? Origins of the Christian holy places. *Journal of Early Christian Studies* 2: 257–271
- Musa, Ghazali, Shahrul Najmin, Thinaranjeneey Thirumoorthi, and Azni Taha (2017). Examining Visitors’ Experience with Batu Cave, Using the Four Realm Experiential Theory. *International Journal of Tourism Cities* 3: 105–20.
- Olsen, Daniel (2012). Negotiating Identity at Religious Sites: A Management Perspective. *Journal of Heritage Tourism* 7: 359–66.
- Olsen, Daniel (2013). A Scalar Comparison of Motivations and Expectations of Experience within the Religious Tourism Market. *International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage* 1: 5
- Raj, Razaq, and Kevin Griffin (2015). *Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage Management: An International Perspective*. Wallingford: Cabi.
- Raj, Razaq. 2012. Religious Tourist’s Motivation for Visiting Religious Sites. *International Journal of Tourism Policy* 4: 95–105.

- Ramírez, Rafael, and Manuel Fernández. 2018. Religious Experiences of Travellers Visiting the Royal Monastery of Santa María de Guadalupe (Spain). *Sustainability* 10: 1890.
- Rubiés, Joan-Pau and Bacon, Francis (2000). *Travel writing as a genre: facts, fiction and the invention of scientific discourse in early modern Europe. International Journal of Travel and Travel Writing*, 5 (33). pp. 5-33. ISSN 1465-2609.
- Ruiz, Jorge R. (2009). "[Sociological discourse analysis: Methods and logic](#)". *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*. **10** (2): Article 26.
- Shackley, Myra (2001). *Managing Sacred Sites: Service Provision and Visitor Experience*. London: Cengage Learning EMEA.
- Shaw, Sarah (2015). Crossing the wilderness: how the Buddha narrates his own travels, Oxford Centre for Buddhist Studies. <https://ocbs.org/crossing-the-wilderness-how-the-buddha-narrates-his-own-travels/>
- Shinde, Kiran (2007). Case study 6: Visiting Sacred Sites in India: Religious Tourism or Pilgrimage. In *Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage Management: International Perspective*. Wallingford: Cabi, pp. 184–97.
- Simone-Charteris, Maria, and Stephen Boyd (2010). The Development of Religious Heritage Tourism in Northern Ireland: Opportunities, Benefits and Obstacles. *Turizam: međunarodni znanstveno-stručni časopis* 58: 229–57.
- Sotinel, Claire, (2005). Les lieux de culte chrétien et le sacré dans l'Antiquité tardive. *Revue de l'histoire des religions*, 222.4: 411–434; repr. as Places of Christian worship and their sacralization in late antiquity. In: Claire Sotinel. 2010. *Church and Society in Italy and Beyond*, 1–19. Farnham: Ashgate/Variorum
- Strong, J.S. (2001). *The Buddha: A Beginner's Guide*, Oneworld Publications, ISBN 978-1-78074-054-6
- Sykes W.H. (1841). Notes on the Religious, Moral, and Political State, *The Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland*, Vol. 6, No. 2 (1841), 248-484.
- Terzidou, Matina, Caroline Scarles, and Mark Saunders. 2018. The Complexities of Religious Tourism Motivations: Sacred Places, Vows and Visions. *Annals of Tourism Research* 70: 54–65.
- Tobón, Sandra, and Natalia Tobón (2013). Turismo Religioso: Fenómeno Social y Económico. *Anuario Turismo y Sociedad* 14: 237–49.
- Thompson, Car (2011). *Travel writing*. Taylor & Francis, Ltd. United Kingdom.
- Vukonic, Boris. 2002. Religion, Tourism and Economics: A Convenient Symbiosis. *Tourism Recreation Research* 27: 59–64.
- Wang, Wanfei, Joseph Chen, and Keji Huang (2016). Religious Tourist Motivation in Buddhist Mountain: The Case from China. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research* 21: 57–72.
- Xuanzang (1996). *The Great Tang Dynasty record of the Western Regions*. Translated by Li Rongxi and Jung-hsi Li, Numata Center for Buddhist Translation & Research, .